

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI,
IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
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CHANGES IN THE STRUCTURE OF AGRICULTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: In this scientific article, an in-depth analysis of the structural changes taking place in the agrarian sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their economic and statistical aspects was carried out. In recent years, such directions as the modernization of agriculture, increasing production efficiency, rational use of land resources, the development of a system of agro-services based on science and innovation are considered as one of the priorities of Public Policy. In this regard, the article analyzes the volume of production of agricultural products, the level of productivity, the role of farmers and peasants in the development of the sector on the basis of accurate statistical indicators.

Key words: Agriculture, farming, agriculture, structural changes, economic analysis, statistical methods, livestock, farming, productivity, investment.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasining agrar sektorida yuz berayotgan tarkibiy o'zgarishlar, ularning iqtisodiy va statistik jihatlari chuqur tahlil qilingan. So'nggi yillarda qishloq xo'jaligini modernizatsiya qilish, ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish, yer resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish, ilm-fan va innovatsiyalarga asoslangan agro-xizmatlar tizimini rivojlantirish kabi yo'nalishlar davlat siyosatining ustuvor vazifalaridan biri sifatida qaralmoqda. Shu munosabat bilan maqolada qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish hajmi, hosildorlik darajasi, fermer va dehqon xo'jaliklarining sektor taraqqiyotidagi o'rni aniq statistik ko'rsatkichlar asosida tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, fermer xo'jaligi, dehqon xo'jaligi, tarkibiy o'zgarishlar, iqtisodiy tahlil, statistik usullar, chorvachilik, dehqonchilik, hosildorlik, investitsiya.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье подробно проанализированы структурные изменения, происходящие в аграрном секторе Республики Узбекистан, их экономические и статистические аспекты. В последние годы в качестве одного из приоритетов государственной политики рассматриваются такие направления, как модернизация сельского хозяйства, повышение эффективности производства, рациональное использование земельных ресурсов, развитие системы агросервисов на основе науки и инноваций. В связи с этим в статье анализируются объемы производства сельскохозяйственной продукции, уровень урожайности, роль фермеров в развитии отрасли на основе конкретных статистических показателей.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, крестьянское хозяйство, структурные изменения, экономический анализ, статистические методы, животноводство, сельское хозяйство, урожайность, инвестиции.

INTRODUCTION

The sustainable development of the economy of our country cannot be imagined without an agricultural sector. This area plays an important role in providing the population with food products, raw materials for industries.

Therefore, our country is undergoing gradual economic reforms in order to develop the agrarian sector steadily. It is possible to achieve high economic efficiency through the rational use of investment, labor, material and innovative potential [1].

At the moment, the necessary legal, organizational and economic measures for the development of small business activities are being implemented in stages. In particular, within the framework of the "Agricultural

DISCUSSION

Statistical analysis in 2020 shows that farms have increased the number of large-horned cattle by nearly 3.9 times compared to 2000. The number of sheep and goats increased by 15.4 times and the number of poultry by 31.1 times. In peasant farms, however, these figures were 2.6, 3.0 and 5.8 times, respectively. In the total farm cross-section, however, the number of livestock increased by 2.4; 2.5 and 6.1 times, respectively. These have also led to a significant increase in meat, milk and egg production [8].

In 2020, farms produced 112.2 thousand tons of meat, 519.8 thousand tons of milk, 1048.9 million eggs. In the case of peasant farms, meat production reached 2302.7 thousand tons, milk – 10372.2 thousand tons, eggs – 4819.9 million units. This means that farms in this category play a decisive role in ensuring the food security of the population.

It can also be seen that farms have achieved significant results in terms of agricultural crops. For example, the gross yield of cereals increased 10.9 times compared to 2000, vegetables – 28.4 times, and fruits – 33.9 times. And the volume of growing grapes increased by 6.8 times.

Productivity indicators have also grown at a positive pace. Grain yields ranged from 27.0 s/ha to 41.8 s/ha, while fruit yields ranged from 56.9 s/ha to 116.7 s/ha. In particular, the yield of grapes increased by 2.4 times from 63.1 s/ha to 152.0 s/ha.

At the same time, as a result of the optimization of the number of farms, 218.6 thousand farms in 2009 decreased by 78.6 thousand by 2015, although the area of land per farm increased by 2.74 times and amounted to 74 hectares. This has led to the efficient use of resources.

In 2020, the average amount of milk milked from a cow was 2,321 kg in total farms, while in farms this figure was 1,769.2 kg, and in peasant farms it was 2,371.8 kg.

As a result of the extensive development of the farm movement, there was an increased sense of land ownership among the villagers, who were financially interested in labor and achieved an increase in the well-being of life [9].

As of the end of 2021, the volume of products and services produced in rural, forest and fishing farms has reached 317.8 trillion soums. Of this, agriculture and livestock accounted for 307.5 trillion soums, forestry for 7.6 trillion soums, and fishing for 2.7 trillion soums.

The highest production volume in the regions cross-section was recorded in Samarkand (41.2 trillion soums), Andijan (32.0 trillion soums) and Tashkent (30.7 trillion soums) regions. The lowest rates were observed in Syrdarya, Karakalpakstan and Navoi regions.

Production rates were highest in Samarkand, Surkhandarya and Namangan regions at around 104.6%. In the regions of Kashkadarya, Bukhara and Fergana, the rate was slightly lower – between 102.2% and 103.7%.

In 2021, 65.9% of agricultural production fell on farms, 29.2% on farms, and 4.9% on organizations engaged in agricultural activities. In the cross-section of the regions, the highest share of farmers was in Samarkand region (38.0%), the share of peasants was in Navoi region (75.4%), and the share of agricultural organizations was in Tashkent region (12.1%) [10].

CONCLUSION

Based on the above analyses, the following important conclusions and suggestions can be advanced:

Further improvement of the methodology of agricultural statistics is necessary. In this case, it is necessary to expand the system of assessment of the activity of the field through statistical observations (i.e., sampling, survey and monographic methods).

It is necessary to develop a system of special statistical indicators on indicators such as product cost, productivity, profit, and regularly analyze them.

It is necessary to carry out comparative analysis, identifying territorial differences in the production of agricultural products through economic indices, correlational and regressive models.

It is necessary to identify structural changes arising under the influence of various internal and external factors, evaluate them through complex statistics and develop reasonable scientific and practical proposals.

through the development of multidisciplinary farms, it is possible to increase not only the volume of production, but also the employment and well-being of the population. Therefore, specific and effective programs should be developed by the state to support this area.

As a result of the large-scale reforms carried out in the agrarian sector of Uzbekistan, especially the development of farms and farmers, the volume of agricultural production increased significantly. Based on statistical analysis, it is determined that farms are rapidly adapting to market demand and are effectively using resources. Peasant farms, on the other hand, play a key role in providing the population with food.

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